

Superconducting 2D NbS₂ Grown Epitaxially by Chemical Vapor Deposition

Zhenyu Wang^{1,2†}, Cheol-Yeon Cheon^{1,2†}, Mukesh Tripathi^{1,2}, Guilherme Migliato Marega^{1,2}, Yanfei Zhao^{1,2}, Hyun Goo Ji^{1,2}, Michal Macha³, Aleksandra Radenovic³, Andras Kis^{1,2*}

¹*Institute of Electrical and Microengineering, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland*

²*Institute of Materials Science and Engineering, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland*

³*Institute of Bioengineering, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), CH-1015 Lausanne, Switzerland.*

**Correspondence should be addressed to: Andras Kis, andras.kis@epfl.ch*

†These authors contributed equally

ABSTRACT

Metallic two-dimensional (2D) transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) are attracting great attention because of their interesting low-temperature properties such as superconductivity, magnetism and charge density waves (CDW). However, further studies and practical applications are being retarded by difficulties in synthesizing high-quality materials with a large grain size and well-determined thickness. In this work, we demonstrate epitaxial chemical vapor deposition (CVD) growth of 2D NbS₂ crystals on a sapphire substrate, with a thickness-dependent structural phase transition. NbS₂ crystals are epitaxially aligned by the underlying c-plane sapphire resulting in high-quality growth. The thickness of NbS₂ is well controlled by growth parameters to be between 1.5 to 10 nm with a large grain size of up to 500 μm. As the thickness increases, we observe in our NbS₂ a transition from a metallic 3R-polytype to a superconducting

2H-polytype, confirmed by Raman spectroscopy, aberration-corrected scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) and electrical transport measurements. Berezinskii-Kosterlitz-Thouless (BKT) superconducting transition occurs in the CVD-grown 2H-phase NbS₂ below a transition temperature (T_c) of 3 K. Our work demonstrates thickness and phase-controllable synthesis of high-quality superconducting 2D NbS₂, which is imperative for its practical applications in next-generation TMDC-based electrical devices.

KEYWORDS: *two-dimensional superconductors, phase transition, CVD, transition metal dichalcogenides, niobium disulfide*

INTRODUCTION

Semiconducting two-dimensional (2D) transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs) have been heavily studied owing to their layer-number dependent bandgap¹ and outstanding performance as field-effect transistors² and optoelectronic devices.³ In contrast to semiconducting TMDCs, metallic TMDCs (*e.g.*, NbS₂, NbSe₂) are attracting great attention in the context of realizing 2D metal-semiconductor junctions with semiconducting TMDCs^{4,5} with the aim of lowering contact resistance by weakening Fermi level pinning.⁶ They are expected to be ideal 2D metal electrodes thanks to their van der Waals (vdW) interaction and small lattice mismatch with other TMDCs,⁷ enhancing electrical performance compared to conventional 3D metal electrodes. Additionally, these metallic TMDCs hold interesting low-temperature properties such as superconductivity,^{8,9} magnetism¹⁰ and charge density waves^{11,12} (CDW), where superconducting TMDCs could be used to observe Andreev reflection in 2D systems^{13,14} and realize Josephson junctions.¹⁵ Among metallic TMDCs, 2H-NbS₂ is a peculiar case in that it is the only superconductor with no CDW instabilities observed experimentally.⁸ This is unusual if compared with other isostructural and isoelectronic 2H-NbSe₂ and 2H-TaS₂, where superconductivity coexist with CDW order. Theoretical work, however, points out 2H-NbS₂ is on the verge of CDW order in the 2D limit¹⁶ or even close to spin density wave instabilities¹⁷ possibly induced by magnetic impurities.¹⁸ This makes 2D NbS₂ an appealing material platform to explore quantum phase transition. These interesting electronic properties and its potential

device applications motivate the development of methods to synthesize 2D metallic and superconducting NbS₂.

Niobium disulfide (NbS₂) mainly exists in two polytypes: rhombohedral (3R) and hexagonal (2H), which exhibit distinct electrical properties. In 3R-NbS₂, metallicity has been confirmed with a minimum resistance at around 30 K.¹⁹ On the other hand, superconductivity can be observed in 2H-NbS₂ bulk below a transition temperature (T_c) of 6 K.⁸ These two phases can be selectively grown in bulk by changing the sulfur pressure,²⁰ whereas reports on control over the polytypes in the few-layer limit are rare. Although 2D NbS₂ can be obtained by mechanical exfoliation from bulk crystals,^{21,22} the flakes are usually several μm in size with little control over the thickness. In recent years, several attempts for growing NbS₂ using CVD have been reported.^{19,23,24} Nevertheless, only 3R-phase metallic NbS₂ has been grown, with a limited domain size and lack of precise layer number control. Growing large-grain and superconducting 2H-phase NbS₂ with controllable thickness has not been reported yet, hindering exploration of 2D superconducting properties and further applications in electrical devices.

Here, we demonstrate epitaxial CVD growth of 2D NbS₂ single crystals and continuous transition from a metallic 3R-polytype to superconducting 2H-polytype with respect to its thickness. Our NbS₂ flakes have a rectangular shape with a large grain size exceeding 500 μm and are highly-aligned by quasi van der Waals epitaxy with atomically smooth sapphire surface. The thickness can be tuned from 1.5 nm to 10 nm by different growth conditions. The thickness-dependent phase transition was clearly observed from Raman and STEM study, which is further confirmed by transport

measurements for different phases, including the observation of superconductivity in layered 2H-NbS₂ below a transition temperature of 3 K.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2D NbS₂ grown by CVD. 2D NbS₂ was grown using a home-built CVD reactor schematically presented in Figure 1(a). C-plane sapphire was used as the growth substrate and was annealed in air for 6 h prior to growth, resulting in a clean surface with atomically smooth step terraces,²⁵ which is crucial for achieving epitaxial growth.²⁶ A solution of niobium chloride (NbCl₅) was used as the precursor, while sodium chloride (NaCl) was used to reduce nucleation density²⁷ and the reaction energy barrier.²⁸ Both solvents were spin-coated on top of sapphire substrate before loading into the chamber. During the growth, as shown in Figure 1(a), another bare sapphire wafer was placed on top of the spin-coated wafer. This promotes the growth of larger crystals by localizing the NbCl₅ vapor and reducing the flow rate of H₂S near the substrate.

We observe different morphologies of our CVD-grown NbS₂ crystals, depending on the growth parameters. Optical micrographs of CVD-grown NbS₂ crystals are shown in **Figure 1(b)** and Supplementary Figure S1. As can be seen from the figures, the shape and thickness of NbS₂ flakes show a clear trend, changing from thick triangles to thin rectangles with increasing temperature. It is notable that the rectangle-shaped NbS₂ flakes are grown with a large domain size having a typical length exceeding 500 μm and a width of around 40 μm , which is significantly larger than those in previous reports.^{19,23,29} In addition, all the rectangular NbS₂ flakes are perfectly aligned to the

same direction, confirmed by the orientation histogram shown in Supplementary Figure S2 for the same region as shown in **Figure 1(b)**. The single crystalline structure was confirmed by selected area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns on several areas of an NbS₂ flake as shown in Supplementary Figure S3. The different crystal morphologies and the orientation of rectangular NbS₂ can be explained by the temperature-dependent strong interaction between NbS₂ and the sapphire substrate.³⁰ At the early stages of growth, nucleation takes place on the surface of sapphire with an initial random orientation of the crystallites.³¹ For relatively low growth temperatures (*e.g.*, 750 °C), the small crystallites do not have enough thermal energy to explore the energy landscape by rotation before they grow to big crystals. As a result, NbS₂ crystals with a small domain size and a random orientation are observed in Supplementary Figure S1(a). We also observe a higher nucleation density under these conditions because of weak thermal etching. On the other hand, at higher growth temperatures (850 °C and 950 °C, Supplementary Figure S1(b) and **Figure 1(b)**), the orientation of the grown NbS₂ is determined by the underlying sapphire. This could be related to the orientation of step edges on the atomically smooth sapphire surface. An AFM image of rectangular NbS₂ crystals from the sample shown in Figure 1(b) is presented in **Figure 1(c)** which clearly shows that the long edges of the NbS₂ crystal are oriented along the step edges on the surface of sapphire. In addition, we note that the smaller triangular NbS₂ crystals both on sapphire and on the NbS₂ thin film are epitaxially aligned along the $[1\bar{1}00]$ axis of the underlying c-plane sapphire (see Supplementary Figure S5), which can be explained by van der Waals interaction with the underlying substrate.³²

Growth morphologies can be also modulated by the gas flow ratio of H₂S and Ar. Dendritic NbS₂ crystals were observed in Supplementary Figure S1 (c) and (d) with a relatively lower value of H₂S:Ar compared to that in Figure 1(b). The morphology transition induced by the gas flow ratio can be explained by the growth rates of different edge terminations.³³ In our case, the NbCl₅ precursor is reduced by H₂S and tiny NbS₂ seeds emerge at the early stage of growth. Along the edges of these tiny seeds, Nb and S atoms are exposed to the reactor atmosphere on zigzag edges³³ with high chemical reactivity. They encounter atoms diffusing on the surface in random collisions and new chemical bonds are formed to achieve the most energetically stable structure.³⁴ Assuming that the spin-coated NbCl₅ provides the same amount of Nb precursor, the probability of meeting and bonding with free atoms depends on the partial pressure of H₂S. When the sulfur supply rate is at an insufficient level (*e.g.*, H₂S : Ar = 1:8), S-terminated edges have much higher possibility to meet free Nb atoms, which leads to a higher growth rate of S-terminated edges than Nb-terminated edges. The difference in growth rates causes the dendritic shapes shown in Supplementary Figure S1 (c) and (d). As H₂S increases to a saturated level (*e.g.*, H₂S : Ar = 1:3), both S and Nb-terminated edges have enough opportunity to bond with free atoms, resulting in similar growth rates of these two type of edges. As a consequence, crystals grow with regular shapes and sharp edges as shown in Figure 1(b).

Different phases of CVD-grown NbS₂. We find that our CVD-grown rectangular NbS₂ crystals can have both 3R and 2H-phase structures, depending on the thickness. Figure 2(a) illustrates the atomic structures of NbS₂ with 3R and 2H polytype stacking.

Each layer is composed of a 1H single layer where the Nb atoms are coordinated in a trigonal prismatic shape, while adjacent layers interact *via* the van der Waals force and maintain the interlayer distance of around 0.7 nm.²⁹ The two polytypes are distinguished by relative rotation and atom alignment between the neighboring planes.³⁵ Atomic force microscopy (AFM), Raman spectroscopy and aberration-corrected STEM were further conducted to investigate the correlation between the phase transition and thickness.

Changing the NbCl₅ concentration allows us to control the thickness of rectangular NbS₂ crystals in the 1.5 nm to 10 nm range, corresponding to 2-16 layers. A histogram of the thickness distribution of as-grown NbS₂ crystals for different pre-coated NbCl₅ concentrations is shown in Supplementary Figure S6, indicating that a higher NbCl₅ concentration leads to a higher dominant thickness. On Figure 2(b) we show an AFM image of a rectangular NbS₂ single crystal with a thickness of 10 nm. A smooth surface and sharp edge can be clearly seen, indicating that our NbS₂ samples have a high crystallinity and good quality. Additional AFM images with various thicknesses ranging from 1.5 nm to 10 nm are shown in Supplementary Figure S7. Figure 2(c) shows the room-temperature Raman spectra acquired from as-grown rectangular NbS₂ crystals with various thicknesses on sapphire substrate. The blue curve presents the Raman spectrum from 3 nm-thick NbS₂ showing two characteristic peaks at 348 cm⁻¹ (E₂) and 389 cm⁻¹ (A₁), which corresponds with the 3R-phase NbS₂.³⁶ The orange curve on the other hand, collected from 10 nm-thick NbS₂ is characterized by peaks located at 340 cm⁻¹ (E¹_{2g}) and 379 cm⁻¹ (A_{1g}), in agreement with the spectral

signature of the 2H-phase NbS₂.³⁶ Data from the 4 nm-thick NbS₂ (purple curve) shows a mixture of Raman spectra for both 3R-phase and 2H-phase, indicating the transition between 2H and 3R occurs around this thickness.

The atomic structures of different phases and stackings can be directly visualized by employing aberration-corrected STEM. We show on Figure 2 (d)-(f) high-resolution high annular angular dark field (HAADF)-STEM images obtained from transferred NbS₂ samples to distinguish different atomic structures and stacking arrangements with various thicknesses. The inset of Figure 2(d) shows a low-magnification HAADF image of a rectangular NbS₂ crystal transferred onto a TEM grid. The HAADF intensity is proportional to the square of the atomic number ($\sim Z^2$), allowing Nb and S atoms to be directly distinguished based on the contrast of individual atomic columns. In Figure 2(d), bright hexagonal rings (Nb atoms) with darker spots (S atoms) in the center are displayed, indicating that the Nb atoms mismatch slightly without any rotation between adjacent layers (illustrated in Figure 2(a)), corresponding to a 3R-polytype stacking. On the other hand, equal intensity of each Nb atom in Figure 2(e) reveals that they are aligned to each other with opposite direction between adjacent layers (illustrated in Figure 2(a)), and that 3 Nb atoms can be found around a single S atom, suggesting a 2H-polytype stacking. Additionally, a mixture of 3R and 2H polytype stacking is observed in Figure 2(f). S line defects are visible close to the interfaces of different stackings, whereas S points defects are present everywhere on the image. A few of the defect positions are highlighted by yellow circles on the corresponding filtered image in Supplementary Figure S9. Additionally, Energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometry

(EDX) spectrum and mapping was also carried out on the transferred samples to confirm the chemical composition and material quality (see Supplementary Figure 10).

Electrical transport in 2D NbS₂ with different phase structures. In order to characterize the electrical transport properties of CVD-grown NbS₂ crystals with different phases, multiterminal devices were fabricated after the crystals have been transferred onto a Si/SiO₂ substrate. Figure 3(a) displays an optical micrograph of a Hall bar device based on a 10 nm-thick NbS₂ crystal. NbS₂ devices with various other thicknesses are shown in Supplementary Figure S11. The detailed fabrication process can be found in the Methods section.

To examine the relationship between the thickness-dependent structural phase and its transport properties, temperature dependence of four-probe longitudinal resistance (R_{xx}) was measured at zero magnetic field, with results for three representative thicknesses (3 nm, 4 nm, and 10 nm) shown in Figure 3(b). Inset shows the magnified view in the 1.5 K - 10 K temperature range. For the sample with a thickness of 3 nm (blue curve), the resistance linearly decreases as the temperature is lowered, indicating its metallic property ($dR/dT > 0$), consistent with previous predictions.³⁷ However, its resistance starts to slightly increase below 20 K where the resistance minimum is observed (See Supplementary Figure S12). Similar observations of this low-temperature resistance minimum were reported in CVD grown 3R-phase NbS₂,^{19,29} which is attributed to electron scattering at defect or excess Nb sites. From the device, we do not observe the superconducting transition above our experimental base temperature (1.4 K). These electrical properties agree well with the metallic nature

of the 3R-phase NbS₂. On the other hand, for the 2H-phase sample with a thickness of 10 nm (shown as orange curve), the resistance drops sharply to zero at around 3 K, indicating the superconducting transition. The superconducting transition critical temperature T_c is 2.6 K, which corresponds to the temperature at which the resistance becomes half of the normal-state resistance (R_N), $R(T_c) = 0.5 R_N$. At the intermediate thickness (4 nm) between the 2H and 3R phase of NbS₂ (shown as the purple curve), interestingly, the resistance drops sharply at around 3 K but remains at a relatively high value ($\sim 150 \Omega$) down to the base temperature of 1.4 K. This feature could be explained by the presence of mixed 2H and 3R phases where metallic 3R-phase and superconducting 2H-phase domains coexist. Notably, this 4 nm-thick device shows metallic behavior at high temperatures but with a slower resistance change (dR/dT) than that of the other 2H and 3R devices. This leads to a lower residual resistance ratio (RRR) of ~ 1.5 , defined as the ratio between the resistance at $T = 300$ K and the normal-state resistance above the superconducting transition temperature of the 2H phase, at $T = 10$ K, which is lower than that of the 3 nm-thick 3R-phase (~ 3.3) and 10 nm-thick 2H phase (~ 11). Since RRR is commonly used as an indicator of the crystalline quality of a superconductor,^{38,39} a smaller RRR in 4 nm-thick NbS₂ indicates the existence of additional structural disorder, which we attribute to sulfur point and line defects between 2H and 3R phases, as confirmed by the STEM results in Supplementary Figure S10. Magnetic field cooling suppresses this sharp resistance drop (shown in Supplementary Figure S13), which further supports the hypothesis that the resistance drop is related to the superconducting transition of the 2H domains. Figure 3(c) displays

four-probe DC V - I characteristics for NbS₂ with different structural phase at the base temperature (1.4 K). A linear curve was obtained for the 3 nm-thick 3R-phase NbS₂ sample, whereas a strong non-linear curve was obtained for the 10 nm-thick 2H-phase NbS₂, consistent with a Berezinskii-Kosterlitz-Thouless (BKT) type superconducting phase transition. Compared to single-phase samples, the V - I curve of the 4nm-thick sample shows a weak non-linear curve (a possible combination of 2H and 3R-phase signal) but with a larger noise, which could be related to contributions from line defects separating the two phases. These results, consistent with Raman and STEM results, provide additional evidence that transition from the metallic 3R-polytype to the superconducting 2H-polytype takes place in our thickness-controlled CVD-grown NbS₂ crystals.

Superconductivity of 2H-phase NbS₂. To further study the superconductivity of CVD-grown 2H NbS₂ crystals, both four-probe DC and AC transport measurements were performed. Figure 4(a) shows the temperature dependence of resistance (R_{xx}) of the device shown in Figure 3(a) at various out-of-plane magnetic fields B , applied perpendicularly to the 2D crystal plane. In the presence of the magnetic field, we define the critical temperature T_c as the temperature at which the resistance decreases to 80% of the normal resistance value. As the amplitude of the magnetic field increases, the critical transition temperature decreases and the resistance change becomes more gradual. A metallic behavior without resistance drop was obtained above the magnetic field of 0.6 T, indicating that superconductivity is completely suppressed by the magnetic field. Figure 4(b) shows the magnetic field-dependent transition, H_{c2} vs T_c/T_{c0}

phase diagram where H_{c2} is the upper critical field and T_{c0} the critical temperature at zero magnetic field. We find a linear relation between H_{c2} and T_c , which is a typical feature of 2D superconductors.^{40,41} It can be fitted with a model from the linearized Ginzburg-Landau (GL) theory,⁴² $H_{c0}(T) = \frac{\phi_0}{2\pi\xi_{GL}(0)^2} \left(1 - \frac{T}{T_c}\right)$, where $\xi_{GL}(0)$ is zero-temperature coherence length, and ϕ_0 is magnetic flux quantum. From the fitted result, we get $\xi_{GL}(0) = 25$ nm, which is larger than the probed sample thickness (10 nm). This indicates that the 2D superconducting transition should follow the BKT type transition. Figure 4(c) shows the four-probe DC I - V characteristics as a function of temperature for the 6 nm-thick 2H-phase NbS₂ device. At 3.5 K, linear Ohmic behavior was obtained with the constant slope of resistance around 3 Ω , which is equal to the metallic normal-state resistance (shown in Supplementary Figure S14). As the temperature decreases, the curve becomes non-linear and a critical current gap is observed at which the probe voltage is close to zero. The V - I curves plotted on a logarithmic scale (shown in the Figure 4(d)) display a clear transition from a V - I linear dependence to a power-law dependence ($V \propto I^\alpha$) indicating the BKT transition. We estimate the BKT transition temperature (T_{BKT}) to be 3 K at the value of $\alpha = 3$ for our 6 nm-thick NbS₂ crystal. Fitted α values as a function of temperature can be found in the Figure 4(e). The data presented above provides further evidence that our CVD-grown 2H NbS₂ exhibit the features expected from a 2D superconductor.

To further investigate the superconducting critical current, AC differential resistance as a function of DC drain-source current was measured at fixed temperatures ranging from 1.5 K to 3 K as shown in Figure 4(f). Resistance peaks sharply at the

critical current ($190 \mu\text{A}$ at 1.5 K) which indicates the transition from the normal resistive state to the superconducting zero-resistance state. The critical current gradually decreases with an increasing temperature and disappears above 3K as the sample becomes metallic.

CONCLUSIONS

We demonstrate a CVD method to synthesize 2D NbS_2 single crystals with a large size, controllable thickness and epitaxial orientation. The thickness-dependent structural transition from metallic 3R-phase to superconducting 2H-phase was first observed in CVD-grown NbS_2 and was confirmed by Raman spectroscopy, aberration-corrected STEM as well as transport measurements. The CVD-grown 2H-phase NbS_2 behaves as a 2D superconductor, with BKT type superconducting transition occurring below 3 K . Our work demonstrates a practical approach to phase-controllable growth of 2D TMDC superconductors and provides the platform for their widespread use in mesoscopic devices.

METHODS

Material synthesis

Rectangular NbS_2 single crystals were synthesized using the chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method in the home-built system schematically represented on Figure 1(a). Before growth, c-plane sapphire wafers were annealed in air for 6 h and spin-coated with 0.3 mol/L NaCl solution in deionized water as well as NbCl_5 solution in isopropanol (IPA). Afterwards, a sapphire wafer was loaded into the quartz chamber and covered with another bare sapphire wafer. Prior to growth, the reactor tube was

purged with argon to remove residual oxygen and humidity. During the whole growth process, hydrogen disulfide (H_2S) with a flow rate of 35 sccm was delivered to the chamber by using argon as a carrier gas. The growth procedure lasts for 30 min at a temperature of 950 °C and atmospheric pressure. As soon as the growth is finished, the chamber is allowed to cool down naturally. H_2S flow was kept with a flow rate of 5 sccm until the furnace reached a temperature of 150 °C to reduce sulfur vacancies.

Raman spectroscopy

Raman spectra of the NbS_2 flakes were performed on as-grown samples on sapphire substrates. A spectrometer (Renishaw inVia Confocal Raman Microscope) was utilized to collect the spectrum with a 532 nm laser and a grating of 3000 g/mm at room temperature. The excitation spot size is around 1 μm with a power of 1 mW.

Scanning transmission electron microscopy measurements

The as-grown samples were spin-coated with PMMA (poly(methyl methacrylate)) A4 at a speed of 2000 rpm for 60 s and heated on a hot plate for drying at 180 °C for 5 min. After immersing in water for 5 min, the PMMA film together with NbS_2 samples was detached by water tension and picked up using a silicon nitride TEM grid. Subsequently, the samples were baked on a hot plate for drying and promoting the adhesion at 65 °C for 10 min. Finally, the PMMA film was removed by immersing in acetone overnight followed by annealing in high vacuum at 250 °C for 6 h.

High-resolution high-angle annular dark field (HAADF) STEM imaging was performed using a double aberration-corrected FEI Titan Themis, which is equipped with a X-FEG, Super-X EDX detector, and monochromator. The beam convergence

half-angle was set to 20 mrad which corresponds to the HAADF detector 49.5-198 mrad collection angle. The microscope was operated at an accelerating voltage of 80 kV, which is below the electron-beam induced knock-on damage of NbS₂. The electron probe current was set to ~20 pA. To avoid the sample drift, images were acquired at various places using a faster scan with 512×512 pixels and 8 μs dwell times. EDX measurements were performed in both Titan Themis and FEI Talos TEM. EDX spectrum and elemental mapping were processed in Velox software, ThermoFisher Scientific. Inverse fast Fourier transform filtering has been applied to magnified images to enhance the contrast and highlight the atomic structures of different phases.

Sample transfer and device fabrication

The as-grown NbS₂ flakes were transferred from sapphire to SiO₂/Si substrate by using the same method as for the preparation of TEM samples. Afterwards, the samples were spin-coated with PMMA polymer and put on a hot plate at 180 °C for 5 min. Electro-beam lithography was used to pattern the electrodes. Finally, a stack of 2nm/80nm thick Ti/Au was deposited by e-beam evaporation for the electrodes, followed with a lift-off process with acetone to remove the PMMA layer. Between the fabrication steps, samples were kept in the inert Ar environment inside a glovebox to prevent sample degradation in air.

Transport measurements

Cryogenic electrical transport measurements were performed in an ICE Oxford liquid helium continuous flow system with a base temperature of ~1.4 K. Temperature dependent four-probe longitudinal resistance (R_{xx}) were measured using SR860 lock-in

amplifier with an AC probe current $I_{ac} = 100$ nA at 13.3 Hz. DC voltage-current (V - I) characteristics were measured by applying constant DC current with Keithley 2636b sourcemeter while measuring DC voltage with Keithley 2182a nanovoltmeter. Four-probe differential resistance (dV_{ac}/dI_{ac}) were measured using the lock-in amplifier with AC probe current $I_{ac} = 100$ nA at 13.3 Hz while sweeping the DC current.

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SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

Optical micrographs under different growth condition; histogram of orientation distribution; selected area electron diffraction; large-scale TEM images; AFM images from different areas; histogram of thickness distribution with various NbCl₅ concentrations; AFM images with various thicknesses; TEM images of hexagonal NbS₂

flake; EDX analysis; STEM images showing a mixture of 3R and 2H phase; optical micrographs of NbS₂ devices; temperature dependent resistance of NbS₂ devices.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

A.K. initiated and supervised the work. Z.W. performed the CVD-grown NbS₂ flakes with initial assistance of Y.Z. Z.W. and M.M. improved the CVD system with supervision of A.R. Z.W. fabricated the devices with initial assistance of G.M.M. C.Y. and Z.W. designed and performed electrical measurements. M.T. performed STEM measurements and EDX spectroscopy. Z.W. performed AFM and Raman spectroscopy with help of H.J. A.K., Z.W. and C.Y. analyzed the data with input from M.T. and H.J. All the authors contributed to the writing of the manuscript.

COMPETING FINANCIAL INTERESTS

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available in Zenodo at

<http://XXXX> (will be added during proof).

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FIGURES

Figure 1. CVD growth of layered NbS₂ flakes. **a**, Schematic illustration of the hot-wall CVD system for NbS₂ growth. In the chamber, a bare wafer was placed on top of the sapphire wafer which was spin-coated with NaCl and NbCl₅ solutions. **b**, Optical micrograph of as-grown NbS₂ flakes showing rectangular shapes and a large size exceeding 500 μm. The orientation of rectangular NbS₂ flakes is aligned to the same direction. **c**, AFM image of the as-grown NbS₂ on sapphire substrates, from an area shown in (b). NbS₂ seeds are epitaxially aligned along the [1 $\bar{1}$ 00] axis of c-plane sapphire, while the preferred growth orientation of rectangular NbS₂ flakes is determined by the terrace step edges.

Figure 2. Phase transition of CVD-grown NbS₂ flakes. **a**, Side and top views of atomic structures of NbS₂ with 3R-polytype stacking and 2H-polytype stacking. **b**, AFM image of an NbS₂ flake transferred onto a Si/SiO₂ substrate. Inset shows the thickness of NbS₂ to be 10 nm. **c**, Raman spectra at room temperature for as-grown NbS₂ flakes on sapphire substrate. The blue curve corresponds to the 3R-phase in 3 nm-thick NbS₂ flakes, and the orange curve shows the 2H-phase in 10 nm-thick NbS₂. The purple curve corresponds to a mixture of 2H and 3R phase in 4 nm-thick NbS₂. **d-f**, STEM images of NbS₂ flakes with (d) 3R-polytype stacking, (e) 2H-polytype stacking and (f) a mixture of 3R-polytype stacking and 2H-polytype stacking. Inset of (d): A low magnification ADF-STEM image of a NbS₂ flake transferred onto a TEM grid.

Figure 3. Transport properties of CVD-grown 2D NbS₂. **a**, Optical micrograph of a NbS₂ device fabricated on Si/SiO₂ substrate with a flake thickness of 10 nm. Scale bar length: 25 μ m. **b**, Zero-field cooled resistance as a function of temperature for NbS₂ devices with different thicknesses. AC current of 0.1 μ A is used to probe the resistance. Inset: a zoomed-in temperature dependence of resistance from 1.4K to 10 K. **c**, V - I characterization of NbS₂ devices with different thicknesses at the base temperature of 1.4 K.

Figure 4. Superconductivity in 2H-phase NbS₂. **a**, Electrical resistance of the device shown in Figure 3(a) at various out-of-plane magnetic fields B . **b**, Corresponding B vs T_c/T_{c0} diagram from the data shown in (a) with its fitting result. **c**, V - I characterization for 6 nm-thick NbS₂ device from the base temperature to 3.6 K. **d**, V - I curve in (c) replotted on a logarithmic scale showing $V \propto I^\alpha$ behavior, consistent with an expected BKT model. **e**, Power-law dependence ($V \propto I^\alpha$) of the fitting parameter α as a function of temperature from the data shown in (d). Gray dashed line corresponds to $\alpha = 3$, where the BKT transition temperature (T_{BKT}) is estimated to be 3 K for our 6 nm-thick grown NbS₂ flake. **f**, Differential resistance at zero magnetic field as a function of source-drain bias current at different temperatures for the 6 nm-thick NbS₂ device.